

ELIXIR Compute Platform Face-to-Face Event Summary Report 2023

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Background

ELIXIR, the European Research Infrastructure for life science data has five different Platforms focused on life science technical activities - these are Tools, Training, Compute, Data, and Interoperability. The [ELIXIR Compute Platform](#) held their annual Face-to-Face meeting on the 7-8th February, 2023 in Helsinki, Finland. The Face-to-Face meeting was kindly hosted by local Compute Platform Executive Committee member Juha Törnroos, supported through [ELIXIR-Finland](#) and [CSC](#). This year's meeting brought together members of the Compute Platform in order to work on their projects known as Tasks and to facilitate strategic Platform planning for the coming year. A large focus of this event was dedicated to discussing and planning the Platform's strategies to develop the ELIXIR Scientific Programme for 2024-2028.

Event format and content

The event took place in Helsinki, Finland for in-person attendees and a remote stream facilitated online attendance for those unable to join in-person. A total of 36 participants joined the event over the two days. Of these attendees, 25 were in-person and 11 attendees streamed the event online. Before the event took place, additional presentation calls were hosted online to facilitate further time for discussion and work during the Compute F2F event days. Both presentations were successful and provided an overview of the compute work ongoing at ELIXIR-FI & CSC and on sensitive data and AAI usage.

Day 1 of the event was largely internally focused on the ELIXIR Compute Platform activities. Task updates were provided on work undertaken in the three 2022-2023 ELIXIR Compute work plan projects. Thereafter, two working sessions on the 24-28 ELIXIR programme were held. Compute hybrid cloud demos were provided by members of Task 2 to highlight the advancements in this area of work. Usage of Miro, an online whiteboard tool, was successful for capturing ideas and feeding discussion through collaborative brainstorming on the new Compute work plans.

Day 2 of the event focused on external-facing content, synergistic to the Compute Platform and looked at the links beyond the internal work of the Platform members. Talks involved the provision of custom cloud platforms at de.NBI and an overview on the project [Towards European Health Data Space](#) (TEHDAS) which led to discussion on the development of the European Health Data Space (EHDS). This was followed by overviews on current developments in Compute Platform synergistic initiatives such as the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) and [EuroHPC](#).

The event ended with a session on the topic of compute services relating to human and sensitive data which is a key focus area for the 2024-2028 Compute Platform work plans. Examples of discussion topics included enhanced AAI capabilities for sensitive data use, trusted research environments and HPC accounting and provenance. Framing this was a presentation by the [ELIXIR Single Cell Omics Community](#) and a [Genomics Data Infrastructure](#) (GDI) project technical overview

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relating to computational requirements.

Significant event outcomes

- Successful pre-event calls for presentations to allow additional discussion and work time at the in-person event
- Members briefed on ELIXIR All-ExCo January meeting outcomes and background for alignment of Compute to 2024-2028 ELIXIR Scientific Programme
- Current Task presentation updates and alignment for 2024-2028 planning inputs
- Health data and sensitive data project updates from:
 - Towards European Health Data Space (TEHDAS)
 - European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project
- Successful hybrid cloud deployment demonstrations by Compute Platform members
- Overview and alignment discussions on:
 - CSC services and Lumi/EuroHPC overview
 - EOSC and onboarding services overview
 - Provision of custom cloud platforms through de.NBI
- Compute emphasis on training and dissemination discussed
- ELIXIR Community interactions and synergies identified through event engagement:
 - Federated Human Data Community
 - Single Cell Omics Community
- Planning of the Compute Platform work plans 2024-2028
 - Alignment and focus to sensitive/health data compute solutions
 - Extension of AAI capabilities
 - Collaboration and improved alignment on trusted research environments solutions
 - Extension of multi cloud and ELIXIR GA₄GH Cloud solutions
 - Accounting and provenance improvements for HPC

Participant feedback on the event

Post-event survey responses were received from approximately half of the event attendees, providing insights on various aspects of the event. The streaming experience received predominantly positive feedback. However, some respondents pointed out occasional audio limitations during hybrid presentations from remote speakers. The short overview of the hotel's history was well-received and seen as a valuable and enjoyable addition to the event. Participants suggested that future events include more minor local additions, as they would be welcomed by attendees.

Conclusion

The Compute Platform held another successful hybrid F2F event. Progress was made on its current project work and planning was successfully undertaken for the coming year. Looking beyond 2023 and towards the ELIXIR 2024-2028 Programme planning, a great deal of content and synergistic initiatives were identified, discussed and strongly fed into the development of the next ELIXIR Compute Platform work plans.

Members of the ELIXIR Compute Platform in Helsinki, 7th February 2023.